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**ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE FACTORS AND RETENTION IN THE R&D
ORGANIZATION OF FILIPINO ENGINEERS IN GREATER MANCHESTER,
THE UNITED KINGDOM**

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06 October 2023

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Acceptance Page

This thesis titled: “**ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE FACTORS AND RETENTION IN THE R&D ORGANIZATION OF FILIPINO ENGINEERS IN GREATER MANCHESTER, THE UNITED KINGDOM**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Mike Clester Sumadsad Perez is a licensed *Electronics Engineer* from the Philippines and is currently practicing as a *Product Quality Engineer* in a *Semiconductor Wafer Fabrication* site in Stockport, Greater Manchester, the United Kingdom. He has been working in the field of semiconductors and electronics for about nine years. He has been to four multinational R&D-based companies in the same field where he has been taking part in the big 'D' of R&D ensuring the integrated circuits released to customers and used by the world are compliant and with high quality and reliability.

He graduated with the degree of *Bachelor of Science in Electronics and Communications Engineering* from the *Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Sto. Tomas Branch* last 2014 under *CHED Full Merit Scholarship*. He finished his *Diploma in Research and Development Management* with a *Chancellor's List* award last 2021 and is currently finishing his *Master of Research and Development Management* at the *University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños*. The R&D management degree supplemented his engineering educational and professional background and instilled a better worldview of the role of engineers in R&D especially in global RDOs he has worked with.

His research interest is in organizational climate and motivations of engineers in R&D organizations, and migration studies. He is aiming to champion and advocate for migrant S&T skilled workers (scientists, engineers, and researchers) and hopes to contribute to the greater good of the Philippines through his research. *Padayon!*

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Dedication

I dedicate this research to all the Filipino engineers who needed to go abroad to find a greener pasture because of their circumstances in life and other various reasons. We may be far away from our homeland, but we will not forget that whatever we do, we are hoping for the best in our motherland. The contribution that we are imparting in the global arena is a true mark of being Filipinos, who, having scarce resources, are still able to make the world a better place by our silent and low-key contribution from the field where we are tinkering with our hammers of technology and innovation.

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Abstract

This study investigated the factors that define the organizational climate and retention in the Research and Development Organization (RDO) of Filipino engineers who migrated to work at an RDO in Greater Manchester, United Kingdom (UK). It discussed the socio-demographic characteristics of selected migrant Filipino engineers and analysed the organizational climate factors and their retention in the Philippines and the UK. A quantitative research design was used with a survey questionnaire administered to 39 Filipino engineers who migrated from 2019 to 2023 from the Philippines or from other countries and who were not yet British citizens. Results confirmed that organizational climate and socio-demographic characteristics influenced the retention decision of Filipino engineers to stay and work long-term in the RDO in the UK. The proposed strategies focused on the significant organizational climate factors *Autonomy and Freedom, Conflict, Communication, and Encouragement* that can be implemented by R&D managers in retaining Filipino engineers in their RDO. The study provided an understanding of the importance of organizational climate and its significance on Filipino engineers employed inside and outside the country, the initial profiling of migrant Filipino engineers, and the strategies that R&D managers can employ for motivating and retaining knowledge workers like the engineers in the organization.

Keywords: Organizational Climate; Retention in R&D Organization; Migration; Filipino Engineers

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

People or human resources such as the engineers, scientists, researchers, and knowledge workers in the context of Research and Development Management (R&DM), are the most essential element of a Research and Development Organization (RDO) (Cuyno, 1997; Reyes, 1995; GCR, 2020 and DOST-SEI, 2022). They are the *human capital* pillar in the latest Global Innovation Index (GII) which analysis of the indicators showed that the Philippines has a notable pool of creative and talented scientists, engineers, and researchers. However, the Philippines lacks *knowledge-intensive employment* while nurturing *labor productivity growth* in a country abundant with global RDOs in *high-tech manufacturing and exports* (GII, 2022).

The direction of all nations is toward prioritizing human resources. In the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), several goals are on human resources such as educated learners with knowledge and skills (SDG4), the sustainable and inclusive industry (SDG9) where the educated and skilled people can achieve full productive employment, decent jobs, and reasonable pay (SDG 8) by 2030 (SDGS, 2015). This is the direction of all nations, especially developing ones like the Philippines.

The role of engineers is vital in sustainable innovation and national development; however, international migration can siphon the Filipino engineers out of the country. The latest migration reports show an increasing number of Science and Technology (S&T) Filipino emigrants from 2009 to 2018, with *engineers and related professionals* as the second top migrants next to *nurses and healthcare workers* (DOST-SEI, 2022 and WMR, 2022).

In harnessing the full potential of Filipino engineers in global RDOs with manufacturing sites in the Philippines, and retaining them to work in their current organization, it is important to have an organizational climate which is conducive, encouraging, motivating and supportive of innovation and creativity. One imperative in R&D management is for managers and organizations' management to understand the organizational climate which influences the employee such as their behavior, performance, job satisfaction, and even retention in the RDO. Hence, the organizational climate in the Philippines and in UK where Filipino engineers migrated have to be investigated to come with strategies that can retain Filipino engineers in their RDOs.

Statement of the Research Problem

In achieving an innovative, progressive, sustainable, and socio-economically developed country, the role of knowledge workers like the Filipino engineers in their respective RDOs in the Philippines is essential. For S&T policy at the national level and decision-making at the organizational level, the factors affecting the decision of highly skilled Filipino engineers to stay in RDOs in the Philippines or to work in RDOs abroad need to be investigated. In this light the study queried on the following research problems:

1. Why do Filipino engineers stay in or leave the RDO in the Philippines?
2. What are the organizational climate factors in the RDO that influence the retention of Filipino Engineers to work in the RDO in the UK?
3. How do organizational climate factors relate to retention of the Filipino engineers in the RDO?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to assess the organizational climate factors and retention in the RDO of Filipino engineers in Greater Manchester in the UK.

Specific objectives are as follows:

1. Discuss the socio-demographic characteristics of selected migrant Filipino engineers employed in an RDO in the UK;
2. Describe the organizational climate factors and retention in the RDO in the UK and in the Philippines of the selected migrant Filipino engineers;
3. Analyze the relation of the organizational climate factors and the retention in the RDO in the UK and in the Philippines of selected migrant Filipino engineers; and
4. Formulate R&D management strategies that can enhance the organizational climate of the RDO to retain the Filipino engineers in their RDO.

Significance of the Study

The findings from the study can provide insights to Filipino engineers working inside and outside the Philippines as well as R&D managers on the relevance of organization climate in relation to retention of knowledge workers including the engineers. Primarily, this study tested organizational climate factors theorized to influence Filipino engineers to migrate and work long-term in the RDO abroad. The initial socio-demographic characteristics of Filipino engineers working in the RDO in the UK can be basis for policy making in human resource development in the organization and migration policy in the country.

This study hopes to raise awareness among R&D managers, organizations' management, policymakers, government bodies, the academe, and industries in the Philippines on the need for conducive organization climate in the RDOs that will encourage and motivate Filipino engineers to continue working in their current organizations as a countermeasure for international migration.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study used a quantitative research approach focusing on the case of Filipino engineers employed in the RDO in Stockport, Greater Manchester, the UK. Its methodology did not cover cross-sectional and longitudinal study of Filipino engineers' perceptions on organization climate factors and retention in the RDO. The samples and locale of the study was only in Manchester and not across the UK. Hence, findings are limited and cannot be generalized for the Filipino engineers and the RDOs in the Philippines nor the UK.

Furthermore, this study included only the top ten organizational climate factors (OCFs) in the literature. It is suggested for future study, the methodological limitations of the study such as the use of qualitative design, comparative and time-series method studies, and inclusion of supervisors and research managers in the respondents can be undertaken.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study searched for literature on the relationship of organizational climate with employee outcomes such as engagement, performance, and morale. Researchers found that organizational climate for creativity and innovation was a significant factor that directly influenced an individual team member's innovation (Marinova et al., 2018); Zuraik, Kelly & Dyck, 2020); Pirola-Merlo & Mann 2004). In the public sector the study of Mutonyi, Slåtten & Lien (2020) stated the importance of organizational climate for employees' individual creative performance of Filipino engineers. Research on the organizational climate specific to the context of *migrant* Filipino engineers, however, is not found among literature available online.

Characteristics of Migrant Filipino Engineers

The definition of "Filipino engineer" can be defined in several ways. For instance, *Republic Act No. 9292* defines an *Electronics Engineer* as a person who is qualified to hold himself/herself out as a duly registered or licensed *Electronics Engineer* who can legally affix to his/her name the letters "ECE." This is also true for other board examination in engineering programs in the Philippines, while those engineering graduates with no board examination can be called engineers, too such as *Computer Engineers, Metallurgical Engineers, and Mechatronic Engineers*.

The government licensure and engineering undergraduate degrees are not the only way for a professional to become an engineer. At work, engineering roles such tasks assigned or job descriptions in hiring professionals from the fields of computer science, information technology, applied physics, chemistry, and the like. More often,

engineering job roles in the twenty-first century can be acquired through experience and formal and non-formal education such as micro-credentials from short courses.

Moreover, the Department of Science and Technology in the Philippines or DOST (2022) describes “Filipino engineers” as engineering professionals, in the S&T field, with engineering bachelor’s degrees in civil, electronics, mechanical, computer, electrical, etc., regardless of whether they are bored exam passers or not. Additionally, DOST (2022) also describes “engineers,” in general, together with nurses, midwives, and healthcare professionals, in the context of migration, as highly skilled, qualified, educated S&T professionals, with at least a college degree, and who are important in the socio-economic development of the country.

In the published *National Semiconductor Strategy* of the UK (UK Govt, 2023), the description of Filipino engineers falls within the category of high-paying, highly skilled international talent, in the same classification as migrant researchers, academics, and students, being encouraged by the UK government to live and work in the UK. This national strategy is explicit in providing support for the recruitment of talented engineers and providing visa schemes such as *High Potential Individual Visa*, *Scale-Up Visa*, and *Global Talent Visa*. The *Skilled-Worker Visa* is currently the one issued to the Filipino engineers in this study.

Like scientists and researchers, engineers are creative and innovative individuals and often called knowledge workers (Soria, 1991; Reyes, 1991). Being innovative can be comprehended through personality characteristics and behaviors while creativity entails intelligence and intelligent thinking and is also an important part of innovative behavior. (Yogun, Miman & Ateş, 2015)

Some of the characteristics of scientists and researchers related to the innovation and creativity of Filipino engineers are self-direction, value for autonomy,

flexibility, freedom of thought, worldly and practicality about salaries, compensation, and working conditions, technicality, liking to be challenged, and are the embodiment of teamwork and being collaborative. (Cuyno, 1997).

Migration of Filipino Engineers

This study focused on Filipino engineers who migrated to other country, particularly, in the UK. That is, the study touches on international migration which is the transfer of population for a short or longer period of time from one country to another in which the migrants are suitable for employment in the destination country (Battisella & Liao, 2013).

The phenomenon of migration can be best described by the factors that give an individual reason to be dissatisfied with his/her location and attributes of distant places that appear appealing to the individual (Dorigo & Tobler, 1983). The study of Delicado (2019) discussed the factors causing emigration of Portuguese scientists to other countries and these factors are lack of training, means to perform research, and desire to learn new things, improve and collaborate, which are intrinsic in nature.

Moreover, DOST categorizes migrants as temporary or permanent in which permanent migrants are those with the intent of staying for a longer period of time in the country of destination. DOST has noted in the latest migration report that 53.27% of the professional Filipino emigrants in 2014-2018 were in the S&T occupation and that there is a trend of increase compared to the previous years (DOST, 2022).

Organizational Climate Factors (OCFs)

Organizational climate, as a simple analogy to weather and climate, is something that is present and pervasive in the organization and influences the behavior of the personnel. It has several dimensions. The RDO has an organizational climate for innovation, autonomy, recognition, and communication. Thus, an R&D manager needs to create a climate open for new ideas and creativity as well as to maintain professionalism for successful delivery of work. (Lumanta, 1996)

Different studies present different dimensions of organizational climate. Researchers are interchangeably using dimensions, factors, and variables to refer to the different facets of organizational climate. An example of a supportive leadership climate was studied by Schyns, Veldhoven, & Wood (2009) and confirmed a clear association or correlation between job satisfaction and supportive leadership climate, and job satisfaction and individual relative leadership climate.

Six of the nine priori scales for the organizational climate based on the study of Litwin and Stringer (1968) are structure, responsibility, identity, reward, warmth, and conflict in the study of leadership behavior and organizational climate in a non-profit organization (Holloway, 2012). The other remaining variables of Litwin and Stringer (1968) are risk, standard, and support. Sherman & Olsen (1996) also used *Litwin and Stringer's* nine climate dimensions in finding the relationship between organizational climate and performance in the various stages in the project life cycle in RDOs.

An empirical study by Mallah (2016) on organizational climate and internal communication within an organization focused on four key organizational climate factors which were leadership, policies and practices, structure, and channels. The findings revealed that effective internal communication was directly influenced by the consistency of the actions and words of the leader.

The top four dimensions conflict, structure, support, and risk surfaced in the study of Shintri & Bharamanaikar (2017) by considering eleven prominent organizational climate researchers. Organizational climate comprising of empowering leadership, work group cohesiveness, and individual learning orientation has been found to have a positive influence on an employee's creative performance (Mutonyi, Slåtten, & Lien, 2020). Furthermore, Ramirez (2020) correlated organizational climate, organizational learning, and research self-efficacy using the dimensions such as role clarity, leadership, work processes, peer relations, work environment, and communication.

The researchers often used the survey method in studying organizational climate relation to creativity and innovation including Litwin and Stringer (1968), and Amabile (1997). The questionnaire of Litwin and Stringer has nine organizational climate dimensions while the Amabile has eight dimensions. (*See Appendix B Tables 1 and 2 for the complete scales and its descriptions*). The latter's eight climate factors were also adapted by other research exemplified by the theoretical framework for organizational and team climate for creative performance by Lee & Yoo (2020) who focused on organizational encouragement, supervisory encouragement, work group support, sufficient resources, challenging work, freedom, organizational impediments, and workload pressure by Amabile (1997). Besides workload pressure, Lee & Yoo (2020) emphasized the importance of climate factors when creating a positive climate for team members' creativity, productivity, and satisfaction.

In summary, various organizational climate dimensions were derived from the literature and considered as relevant and applicable factors. The factors used in this study were autonomy and freedom, conflict, communication, encouragement, leadership, creativity and innovation, challenging tasks, structure, support, and

identity. A set of criteria in selecting the OCFs that were formulated such as: 1) the number of hits in the literature reviewed; 2) relatability of the context of the literature; and 3) applicability to this study. In each criterion, all the factors were scored from one to five with five being the highest and one being the lowest. All the scores from the three criteria were summed for each factor with 15 as the highest score. The total scores on all the factors were ranked from highest to lowest and the top ten factors were selected as seen in Table 2.1. There is not much difference in the overall score among the factors. The ranking can be validated from the actual responses in the questionnaire that was used in the study.

Table 2.1

Organizational Climate Factors Extracted from Literature

Organizational Climate Factor	Overall Score	Rank
Autonomy and Freedom	13	3
Conflict	13	3
Communication	13	3
Encouragement	12	4
Leadership	15	1
Creativity and Innovation	14	2
Challenging Tasks	12	4
Structure	14	2
Support	15	1
Identity	13	3

Theoretical Framework

Organizational Climate Theory

Organizational Climate is a concept that emerges through the social information processes of employees in an organization, as a result of their experiences on policies, practices, and procedures and from the behaviors they demonstrate which are being rewarded, supported, and expected. It is known that research on organizational

climate tends to have a narrow focus on the shared perceptions of personnel in different contexts. Many researchers have used it to understand how the organizational environment influences organizational outcomes and how they can be changed (Schneider, Ehrhart & Macey, 2016). A number of researchers have studied this area to determine the relationship between organizational climate and different employee outcomes. For instance, the study by Mutonyi, Slåtten & Lien (2020) showed that organizational climate for innovation motivated employees' individual creativity.

The assumptions surrounding *Organizational Climate Theory* are: 1) The behavior of employees is in accordance with their perception of their organizational environment including the ways of working (i.e., procedures, policies, and practices); 2) This perception of the organizational environment is a result of the social processes in the organization as an outcome of the interaction and communication of the supervisors, managers, employees, and other stakeholders.; 3) The perceptions of the organizational environment are perceived by employees differently depending on the facet or topic to which such procedures, policies, or practices refer; and 4) These facet-specific perceptions aid the employees to better understand each topic which enables them to make sense of what is expected of them (Sherman, Hadar & Luria, 2018).

Organizational climate has been studied in different contexts such as climate health and safety (Clarke, Probst, Guldenmund, & Passmore, 2015). There is also an organizational climate specific to creativity and innovation with factors that were found to predict creative performance (Pirola-Merlo & Mann, 2004; Zuraik, Kelly & Dyck, 2020). This organizational climate can also be the team climate in reference to team creativity and team innovation. West (1990) identified the four factors important for the team climate of innovation: vision, participation, task orientation, and support for innovation.

Theories of Creativity and Innovation

The environment that is sought by knowledge workers in an RDO is the climate for creativity and innovation. This is also the climate that would encourage Filipino engineers' retention in their RDO. The goal of R&D management is for RDOs to produce the desired outcome and performance which will be made possible when the creativity of the knowledge workers is nurtured by creating an environment that is conducive to creativity and innovation of the knowledge workers (Soria, 1991; Reyes, 1991).

As such, several theories on creativity help explain the creative environment. One of the theories is the organizational climate model or the componential theory of creativity and innovation which aims to adequately capture all the major elements influencing creativity and innovations in organizations. One of the prominent conceptual models is of Amabile (1996) in which she proved that the dimensions of organizational encouragement, supervisory encouragement, work support groups, sufficient resources, challenging work, and freedom are stimulants of creativity. One of the most important lessons from Amabile (1996) is that R&D managers at all levels should be paying attention to the environment they create for the creative individuals.

A creative environment is a precursor to an innovative climate that produces innovations which are tools for the development of an RDO. Innovativeness comes from an employee, as well as creativity, and thus RDOs should create an environment that fosters innovations, an environment that facilitates innovative practices rather than inhibiting them. Some of the dimensions that were found to have a strong positive correlation with innovative climate are work characteristics, management support, co-worker support, emotional safety, resources, diversity, dynamism, risk-taking, and organizational systems, and processes.

There are also studies that determined the relationship between climate for creativity and organizational innovation using the same dimensions established by Amabile as priori scales. For instance, the study of Shamsuddin and Hamid (2014) has shown that the climate for creativity is significantly related to the four dimensions of organizational innovativeness, product, process, behavior, and market.

Organizational climate in the context of creativity and innovation is equivalent to team climate for innovation where creativity can be viewed as either individual or group creativity. One common knowledge is that individual creativity influences team creativity or that the creativity of the team is dependent on the creativity of individual members perceived or summed altogether.

Creativity is influenced by the *climate for creativity* and unfolds over time. The climate for creativity is a combination of the individual perception of the team members at a team-level factor. Individuals working on different activities or tasks may achieve different degrees of creativity. The measurement of climate for creativity will be high in the group. Even if a single member may demonstrate little creativity in a particular week, their contribution is still important because over time, the individual contributions shape the team outcomes (Pirola-Merlo & Mann, 2004).

Furthermore, the *climate for innovation* is one in which an individual tends to search and experiment for new, sophisticated, and risky capabilities and tools resulting in the improvement of knowledge management capability which is suitable for product innovation. Cai, Liu, Huang, & Liang (2019) validated the moderating role of an innovative climate for agile product innovation. Their study also supports the existing assertions of the importance of an innovative climate among employees to achieve the desired successful outcome of product innovation.

Conceptual Framework

This study investigated OCFs extracted from the literature and used as a measure of the organizational climate of Filipino engineers and analyzed those factors in their context and the relations to their retention in the RDO in the UK and in the Philippines. The retention is the perception or decision of the Filipino engineer to stay long-term to work at an RDO in the UK or to go back and work in an RDO in the Philippines. Below is the conceptual framework of the study:

Figure 2.1

Conceptual Model on Organizational Climate Factors and Retention in the RDO

Operational Definition of Terminologies

Organizational Climate – is an established construct or concept, related to culture, which is part of the internal environment of an organization and is based on the perception of the employees on the various factors and dimensions such as leadership, processes, communication, etc. that influence and motivate employees' behavior.

Organizational Climate Factors in the RDO (OCFs) – are the elements or components based on organizational climate dimensions reviewed from the literature that comprise an organizational climate. The OCFs extracted from the literature used in this study are autonomy and freedom, conflict, communication, encouragement, leadership, creativity and innovation, challenging tasks, structure, support and identity.

RDO – is the abbreviation for R&D organization which is equivalent to the company which is used in the questionnaire to pertain to the previous and current RDO of a Filipino engineer or the respondent.

Retention in the RDO – is the decision of Filipino engineers whether to stay and work in the RDO in the UK or to go back and work at the RDO in the Philippines.

Socio-demographic characteristics – are the attributes of the Filipino engineers in the study such as their age, sex at birth, civil status, number of dependents, level of education, length of work experience, length of stay in the UK, job role aligned with previous work, number of organizations worked with, support to the Philippines, and having relatives in the UK. These also cover Filipino engineers' decision to stay in the UK five years from now, rating on working and external physical environment, company benefits and salary, company rewards and recognition, and perception on migration regulation.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study on organizational climate and retention in RDO of Filipino engineers used the case study approach and survey design. This study also followed a quantitative approach by acquiring and analyzing primary data from the survey. Using the questionnaire as a research instrument, administered to Filipino engineers in the RDO in Stockport, Greater Manchester, the UK.

Locale of the Study

The respondents of the study were Filipino engineers who were hired and relocated to the Stockport, Manchester in the UK from 2019 to 2023 and working in a *Semiconductor* company which is referred to in the study as the RDO. The RDO is located in the region of Greater Manchester (Figure 3.1), which is a metropolitan county in England, Northwest of Great Britain. Greater Manchester is composed of ten boroughs or districts namely Bolton, Bury, Manchester, Oldham, Rochdale, Salford, Tameside, Trafford, Wigan, and Stockport. According to the 2021 ONS census, the population of Greater Manchester is about 2,867,800 while Stockport is 294,800 (ONS UK, 2023).

Cultural diversity is a common feature of Greater Manchester wherein *Asian, Asian British, or Asian Welsh* ethnicity is second comprising 13.6% of the population while in Stockport the same ethnicity group is 7.3%. In terms of the level of qualifications in Greater Manchester and Stockport, the *Highest Level of Qualification Level 4 Qualifications* are 31.9% and 37.6% respectively while *No Qualifications* are 20.0% and 15.5% respectively.

Moreover, the RDO where the Filipino engineers were employed is a fifty-year-old semiconductor wafer fabrication site or a global RDO with integrated circuits as products. According to Glassdoor (2023), there are at least sixty-four electronics manufacturing companies in Manchester.

Figure 3.1

Districts of Greater Manchester

(Source: From ONS / (c) Ordnance Survey)

Data Collection

The survey was administered from June 8 to June 15, 2023, using a *Google* Form and sent to the respondent's preferred channel of communication such as *Facebook* Messenger. Respondents were communicated regarding the research and survey prior to transmission of the *Google* Forms.

Respondents and Sampling Design

The respondents of the survey were Filipino engineers who have migrated, from 2019 to 2023, to the UK from the Philippines or from other countries and who were not yet British citizens as of the survey. A complete enumeration was planned, with questionnaire sent to all 41 Filipino however, only 39 respondents or 95 % submitted and completed the survey.

Instrument

The instrument employed was a survey questionnaire composed of five parts: 1) Informed Consent Form; 2) Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents; 3) Rating on the Organizational Climate Factors; 4) Selection of Top 3 Organizational Climate Factors and Retention decision in the RDO in the UK and the Philippines; and 5) Open-ended Questions (Appendix A for the full research questionnaire).

The majority of the questions employed a five-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). Other questions required answers in the form of information, selection, and short answers.

The questions were crafted from the synthesis of the review of related literature and grounding them to the *organizational climate theory* and *theories of creativity and innovation*. The questions were based on the definition and examples of the factors used by previous studies (i.e., Amabile (1997), and Litwin & Stringer (1968)).

Data Analysis

The socio-demographic characteristics, top three ratings, and perception of the OCFs and retention of the Filipino engineers were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Internal reliability and normality tests were performed before proceeding with the inferential statistical calculations to ensure that the items were able to measure the

perceptions of the Filipino engineers and to determine the appropriate statistical methods to be utilized.

This study used ordinal data for the major items from a survey questionnaire. Hence, nonparametric tests were used in the data analysis after validating that at least one variable was with the assumption of being non-normal. The Mann-Whitney U test was used in comparing two unpaired samples, Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test was used in comparing more than two groups, and Kendall's Tau and Spearman's Rank Correlation were used in checking the correlation between two variables. Likewise, Wilcoxon Sign Rank test was also used in comparing two paired samples.

Non-parametric tests were also conducted the data analysis. The median was used as the central tendency, and the interquartile range was used in presenting the spread of the middle half of the responses since the mean and standard deviation were not found to be appropriately differentiate the factors.

Kendall's Tau, Mann-Whitney U Test, Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test, and Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Test p-values were acquired using the data from *OCFUK* and *RUK*, *OCFPH* and *RPH*, *OCFUK* and *OCFUK*, *Socio-demographics* and *RUK*, and *Socio-demographics* and *RPH*. There were also correlation matrices generated using Spearman's Rank Correlation values to visually show the significant correlation of the twelve factors.

To ensure the validity of the study, internal reliability or consistency of the instrument was also calculated by computing the Cronbach's Alpha of the questionnaire items. A dry run via the response of the initial two respondents was conducted as a pretest prior to sending the questionnaire to the rest of the respondents.

Part four of the questionnaire delved with the other reason(s) not mentioned in the previous questions while part five asked for other comments that the respondent would provide regarding Filipino engineers working in the UK. The responses were analyzed using a word cloud and by simply consolidating and clustering the short answers. Appendix D Figures 1 and 2 provided some key insights supplemental to the quantitative results of this study.

In the generation of visual and numerical summaries, both MS *Excel* and *R Software* were used. As to the calculation of p-values for Kendall's Rank correlation, Mann-Whitney U test, Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test, and Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum test, *R Software* was also utilized. *Jamovi* software was used in calculating the internal consistency of the questionnaire items.

Ethical Consideration

The right to be informed of the respondents was observed in this research. Individually, the purpose of the research was explained to the respondents as part of communication before proceeding to the question sections of the *Google* Form, as well as other information that they needed to know, before consenting if they wanted to take part in the research.

Data privacy and consent of the respondents in the survey were taken into great consideration by aligning to the *UP-Data Privacy Notice*. The link to the complete UP Data Privacy Notice was attached to the *Informed Consent Form* section of the survey so that respondents could access it. Respondents were asked if they would want to partake in the survey. If they verbally consented, they would sign a consent and agreement form on the very first page of the form before filling out all the parts of the questionnaire.

The survey was administered through a *Google* Form which means that even after verbally consenting, the respondent can still opt out of doing the survey. The researcher ensured that sensitive information or information that are not appropriate to be publicized are not to be disclosed outwardly.

Furthermore, the survey did not ask for information that is not deemed appropriate. An example of that information is the name and the salary. For professionals or the working group, salary is a sacred and confidential thing that should not be disclosed. The names of the respondents were not required in the form sheet. The name of the organization where the engineers are working is not disclosed in this paper too.

Lastly, the conduct of the research followed and complied with the requirements of the UP Open University Institutional Research Ethics Committee (UPOU IREC).

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Migrant Filipino Engineers

A total of 39 out of 41 Filipino engineers responded to the survey through Google Forms. Only the *variables age, number of dependents, length of work experience, length of stay in the UK, and the number of organizations worked with* are continuous. The rest are discrete or categorical data as shown in Table 4.1.

Most of the respondents (96%) have an average age of 36 years old, falling in the age range of 25 to 43 years old with a minimum age of 25 and maximum age of 55. In terms of length of work experience, they have been working for an average of 13 years with four years as the minimum and 30 years as the maximum. There are 26% of Filipino engineers with four to nine years of work experience and 70% with nine to 21 years of work experience. Moreover, the average number of organizations where the Filipino engineers have worked is three, and 77% of the Filipino engineers have aligned job roles from their previous companies. This means that the skills of the Filipino engineers were acquired over time and that this is one of the key characteristics of migrant Filipino engineers being skilled workers.

Moreover, most of the respondents (87%) have a bachelor's degree only while only five (13%) have post-baccalaureate degrees as seen in Table 4.1. In Figure 4.1, about 72% of the respondents have bachelor's degrees in *Electronics Engineering* while the rest have other engineering (e.g., electrical, chemical, computer), and applied and pure science (e.g., chemistry, physics) degrees. This means that the RDO in this case study, which is a *Semiconductor* company in nature, has more *Electronics Engineering* graduates who have studied *Semiconductor* manufacturing, electronics,

or *Materials Science and Engineering*. As requirements in working in the RDO in the UK, Filipino engineers should have work experience and education related to their line of work in the recipient country.

Table 4.1

Socio-demographics characteristics of Filipino Engineers

Variable	Measure Type	Mean	Median	Min	Max
Age (years) 25 to 31 – 8 (21%) 31 to 37 – 17 (44%) 37 to 43 – 12 (31%) 43 to 49 – 1 (2%) 49 to 55 – 1 (2%)	Continuous	36	35	25	55
Sex at Birth Male – 22 (56%), Female – 17 (44%)	Discrete	-	0	0	1
Civil Status Single =16 (41%), Married = 23 (59%)	Discrete	-	2	1	2
Number of Dependents With dependents = 24 (62%) With their dependents in the UK=18 (46%)	Continuous	1	1	0	4
Level of Education Bachelor only = 34 (87%), With Master's=4 (11%), With PhD = 1 (2%)	Discrete	-	1	1	3
Length of Work Experience (years) 4 to 9 – 10 (26%) 9 to 15 – 17 (44%) 15 to 21 – 10 (26%) 21 to 26 – 1 (2%) 26 to 30 – 1 (2%)	Continuous	13	13	4	30
Length of Stay in the UK (months) 1 to 14 – 28 (72%) 14 to 27 – 7 (18%) 27 to 40 – 2 (5%) 40 to 53 – 2 (5%)	Continuous	12	7	1	52

Job Role Aligned with Previous Work No (n=9, 23%), Yes (n=30, 77%)	Discrete	-	1	0	1
Number of Organizations Worked With 0 to 4 – 22 (57%) 4 to 5 – 7 (18%) 5 to 6 – 9 (23%) 6 to 8 – 1 (2%)	Continuous	3	3	2	6
Support to the Philippines No = 10 (26%), Yes = 29 (74%)	Discrete	-	1	0	1
Having Relatives in the UK No = 29 (74%), Yes = 10 (26%)	Discrete	-	1	1	2
Decision to Stay in the UK Five Years from Now No=1(2%), Yes=29(75%), Maybe=9 (23%)	Discrete	-	1	0	3
Rating on working environment (transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate, and weather etc.) 3 (n=7), 4 (n=18), 5 (n=14)	Discrete	-	4	3	5
Rating on working environment (in terms of corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems) 3 (n=7), 4 (n=13), 5 (n=19)	Discrete	-	4	3	5
Rating on company benefits and salary. 2 (n=2) 3 (n=12) 4 (n=17) 5 (n=8)	Discrete	-	4	2	5
Rating on company rewards and recognition 1 (n=3) 2 (n=1) 3 (n=18) 4 (n=12) 5 (n=5)	Discrete	-	3	1	5
Migration Regulation No = 5 (13%), Yes = 34 (87%)	Discrete	-	2	1	2

Figure 4.1

Number and percent distribution of bachelor's degree

Other demographic characteristics in Table 4.1 are related to personal attributes of the respondents. The ratio of male and female Filipino engineers is 22:17 while the civil status has a ratio of 16:23 of single and married Filipino engineers. These ratios on sex at birth and civil status do not show substantial disparity. About 62% of the total respondents are with dependents, either with partners and/or children, who are the majority (46%) living in the UK already with them. Even if they do not have dependents, 74% of the Filipino engineers support other individual(s) in the Philippines. All the respondents do not have British or dual citizenship yet. The Filipino engineer with the longest stay in the UK has about 52 months working with the company while there was only one who had just arrived for about a month. Majority of the Filipino engineers (72%) have been staying in the UK for one to 14 months. Given their educational background and skills, the Filipino engineers are able to apply and be hired in their current company in the UK regardless of their sex at birth, civil status, and dependents. Moreover, the respondents having spouses and dependents, and

being breadwinners could also be a reason why they applied for their current company in the UK.

As to staying in the UK long-term, 75% perceived that they will still be working in the RDO in the UK five years from now. This may imply that they will still be adding years of experience in the same or different company to an advantage once they get British or dual citizenship. Having British or dual citizenship will give them leverage for more opportunities such as transferring to another company with better compensation and benefits, especially for those who have shorter work experience and a smaller number of organizations worked with.

Furthermore, the majority of the respondents prefer the working environment in the UK in general. The working environment includes transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate and weather, corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems. In the open-ended question, the majority of the respondents cited that they moved to the UK to have work-life balance and also because there were services from the government in the Philippines that were not desirable. It can be summarized from the answers of the respondents to the open-ended question that their slow career growth, unreasonable workload, and low salary in the Philippines were not creating a good working environment and balanced quality of life. Some respondents cited that the UK government can provide good educational benefits for their children as well as the security for medical benefits.

Regarding the financial aspect, respondents prefer company benefits and salary, as it has a median score of four, compared to company rewards and recognition with a median score of three. This can be interpreted that the rewards and recognition from the previous companies of the respondents were similar but they have more preferable salaries and benefits now. Better company benefits and salary can help

Filipino engineers to support not only their immediate families but also other people depending on them from the Philippines.

Moreover, 87% of the respondents confirmed that the UK has an easy migration regulation while 74% have no relatives in the UK prior to relocating. This means that the visa can be easily accessed by Filipino engineers and that skills and experience are important in visa acquisition rather than having relatives who will help them. There is also an additional benefit of having a dependent visa for the legal dependents of the Filipino engineer. Filipino engineers can work in the RDO in the UK with their families living with them instead of leaving them in the Philippines. Two respondents, including an engineering manager, who have more than fifteen years of experience and dependents, were previously employed in Malaysia and Singapore for many years. They stated in the open-ended question that if only permanent residency was possible in those Asian countries, then they would have not applied to a company in the UK. There are a total of nine respondents whose previous companies were located in Asian countries Taiwan, Singapore, and Malaysia.

Based on the previous results discussed, it is evident that socio-demographic characteristics are attributes in the migration of Filipino engineers to work in their current RDO in the UK. The educational background, the rich experience honed over time from different organizations and job roles, and personal reasons such as having and supporting a family or dependents greatly influenced the decision of Filipino engineers to migrate and work in their current RDO in the UK.

The Shapiro-wilk Test using *R* software, for respondents that are less than 50, was utilized for the checking of the assumptions of the socio-demographic characteristics. Table 4.2 shows that only the variables *age* and *length of work*

experience are normally distributed because their p-values are greater than 0.05 (level of significance) while the rest of the variables did not meet the normality assumption.

Table 4.2

Normality Test of Socio-demographic Characteristics

Variables	p-value	Distribution
Age	0.1018 ns	Normal
Sex at Birth	0.0000****	Not normal
Civil Status	0.0000****	Not normal
Number of Dependents	0.0001***	Not normal
Level of Education	0.0000****	Not normal
Length of Work Experience	0.1866 ns	Normal
Length of Stay in the UK	0.0000****	Not normal
Job Role Aligned with Previous Work	0.0000****	Not normal
Number of Organizations Worked with	0.0001***	Not normal
Support to the Philippines	0.0000****	Not normal
Decision to Stay in the UK Five Years from Now	0.0000****	Not normal
Rating on working environment (transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate, and weather etc.)	0.0000****	Not normal
Rating on working environment (in terms of corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems)	0.0000****	Not normal
Rating on company benefits and salary	0.0003***	Not normal
Rating on company rewards and recognition	0.0002***	Not normal
Migration regulation	0.0000****	Not normal
With relatives in the UK	0.0000****	Not normal

*Significant codes: Signif. Codes: '****' 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 'ns' 1*

Socio-demographic characteristics and retention were compared with different categorizations of the demographics, but it did not show any significant difference. This can be further investigated if there is a larger sample size. See Appendix C.

In terms of other traits, as seen in Appendix D Figure 1, as a result of an open-ended question, respondents wrote down that Filipino engineers have positive attitudes, are responsible, competent, world-class, and are able to adapt to

challenging tasks, experiences, and situations. They are also able to handle multiple tasks assigned to them.

Organizational Climate Factors and Retention

To test if the variables are able to measure the perception of the Filipino engineers, internal reliability of the questionnaire items using *Jamovi* software, was calculated. Table 4.3 shows excellent Cronbach alphas for all the items altogether and even from each separate calculation after dropping one variable at a time.

Table 4.3

Cronbach Alphas of OCFs and Retention in the RDO

Variables	Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
All Variables (For the entire instrument)	1-12	0.950	Excellent
Organizational Factors *Cronbach's Alpha if each item/factor is dropped.	1	0.940	Excellent
	2	0.942	Excellent
	3	0.941	Excellent
	4	0.942	Excellent
	5	0.944	Excellent
	6	0.941	Excellent
	7	0.945	Excellent
	8	0.946	Excellent
	9	0.942	Excellent
	10	0.948	Excellent
Retention in the RDO	11	0.952	Excellent
	12	0.964	Excellent

Cronbach's alpha coefficient interpretation: Unacceptable ($0.5 > \alpha$); Poor ($0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$); Questionable ($0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$); Acceptable ($0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$); Good ($0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$); Excellent ($\alpha \geq 0.9$)

The Shapiro-wilk Test using *R* software, for respondents that are less than 50, was utilized for the checking of the assumptions of the twelve variables of the study.

Table 4.4 shows that all variables have normality assumption.

Table 4.4*Normality Test of OCFs and Retention in the RDO*

Variables	p-value	Distribution
Organizational Climate Factors		
1) I know my job role well and I also have freedom to contribute, decide and take part to projects in my current company. (Autonomy and Freedom)	0.0000****	Not normal
2) I can easily voice out my concerns and give feedback to my supervisors or managers and co-workmates in my current company in the UK. (Conflict)	0.0000****	Not normal
3) I can easily relay information to my team and get response from my supervisors and managers in my current company. (Communication)	0.0001***	Not normal
4) My supervisor in my current company encourages me to solve problems on my own but is willing to support once I ask for help. (Encouragement)	0.0000****	Not normal
5) My manager in my current company in the UK gives me a sense of direction for my performance goals. (Leadership)	0.0000****	Not normal
6) We were encouraged to solve problems and issues creatively in my previous company. (Creative and Innovative Environment)	0.0000****	Not normal
7) My projects and tasks in my previous company are quite challenging. (Challenging Tasks)	0.0000****	Not normal
8) I can easily get approval for the resources that I need for my work in my previous company. (Structure)	0.0000****	Not normal
9) I always get the support that I need from my supervisor and teammates whenever I need help from my previous company. (Support)	0.0001***	Not normal
10) My manager from my previous company has a good training development plan and career growth for me. (Identity)	0.0017**	Not normal
Retention Decision in the RDO		
11) Retention decision to stay and work in RDO in the UK (RUK)	0.0000****	Not normal
12) Retention decision to stay and work in RDO in the Philippines (RPH)	0.0000****	Not normal

*Significant codes: Signif. codes: '****' 0.0001 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 'ns' 1*

The respondents homogenously “agree” on almost all of the variables except for *Identity* and *RPH* as shown on the median values in Table 4.5. This means that they agree on all the OCFs except for *Identity*. They also “agree” on seeing themselves “settling in the UK and working in a company in the UK (long-term) whilst becoming a British resident or citizen” while “disagreeing on working back in a company in the Philippines in the future.”

Table 4.5

OCFs and Retention Median Values

Variables	Median
1) I know my job role well and I also have freedom to contribute, decide and take part to projects in my current company. (Autonomy and Freedom)	4
2) I can easily voice out my concerns and give feedback to my supervisors or managers and co-workmates in my current company in the UK. (Conflict)	4
3) I can easily relay information to my team and get response from my supervisors and managers in my current company. (Communication)	4
4) My supervisor in my current company encourages me to solve problems on my own but is willing to support once I ask for help. (Encouragement)	4
5) My manager in my current company in the UK gives me a sense of direction for my performance goals. (Leadership)	4
6) We were encouraged to solve problems and issues creatively in my previous company. (Creative and Innovative Environment)	4
7) My projects and tasks in my previous company are quite challenging. (Challenging Tasks)	4
8) I can easily get approval for the resources that I need for my work in my previous company. (Structure)	4
9) I always get the support that I need from my supervisor and teammates whenever I need help from my previous company. (Support)	4

10) My manager from my previous company has a good training development plan and career growth for me. (Identity)	3
11) I see myself settling in the UK and working in a company here (long-term) whilst becoming a British resident or citizen. (RUK)	4
12) I see myself working back in a company in the Philippines in the future. (RPH)	2

From the questionnaire, the respondents were also asked to rank the top three items to which they can mostly relate as shown in Table 4.6. The answers revealed that autonomy and freedom, creative and innovative environment, encouragement, conflict, and challenging tasks are the top five answers respectively with autonomy and freedom, conflict, and encouragement as factors from the perspective of an RDO in the UK while creative and innovative environment and challenging tasks as factors from the perspective of an RDO in the Philippines.

Table 4.6

Top Three Organizational Climate Factors

Organizational Climate Factor	n (%)	Rank
1) I know my job role well and I also have freedom to contribute, decide and take part to projects in my current company. (Autonomy and Freedom)	26 (22%)	1
2) I can easily voice out my concerns and give feedback to my supervisors or managers and co-workmates in my current company in the UK. (Conflict)	13 (11%)	4
3) I can easily relay information to my team and get response from my supervisors and managers in my current company. (Communication)	10 (9%)	6
4) My supervisor in my current company encourages me to solve problems on my own but is willing to support once I ask for help. (Encouragement)	16 (14%)	3
5) My manager in my current company in the UK gives me a sense of direction for my performance goals. (Leadership)	6 (5%)	7

6) We were encouraged to solve problems and issues creatively in my previous company. (Creative and Innovative Environment)	15 (13%)	2
7) My projects and tasks in my previous company are quite challenging. (Challenging Tasks)	12 (10%)	5
8) I can easily get approval for the resources that I need for my work in my previous company. (Structure)	4 (3%)	8
9) I always get the support that I need from my supervisor and teammates whenever I need help from my previous company. (Support)	6 (5%)	7
10) My manager from my previous company has a good training development plan and career growth for me. (Identity)	6 (5%)	7

Relation of Organizational Climate Factors and the Retention

Using Spearman's Rank correlation on *R* software, the correlation matrix in Table 4.7 was generated. The matrix shows a significant correlation among the OCFs while there is no correlation between the retention (factors 11 and 12). There is also no correlation between RPH and all the other variables. In the RUK, however, no correlation with the factors of *Leadership* and *Structure* was found.

In the literature review, the leadership factor has the most frequency of hit and has been used in several studies with a significant relationship with organizational outcomes. This study demonstrates that retention has no correlation with the leadership factor. This might be because of possible reasons such as the respondents being the majority are still new to the company and their expectations from their managers are not yet being met as they are still in the training phase. Also, increasing the sample size of the survey can also increase the resolution to see if a larger population of Filipino engineers will perceive leadership factors as also significant OCF.

Table 4.7

Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	1	0.75	0.79	0.78	0.82	0.73	0.62	0.57	0.71	0.48	0.39	-0.11
2	0.75	1	0.85	0.73	0.75	0.7	0.6	0.52	0.65	0.44	0.4	-0.05
3	0.79	0.85	1	0.85	0.8	0.8	0.63	0.48	0.7	0.56	0.55	-0.15
4	0.78	0.73	0.85	1	0.84	0.73	0.61	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.45	-0.1
5	0.82	0.75	0.8	0.84	1	0.67	0.46	0.47	0.61	0.34	0.31	-0.13
6	0.73	0.7	0.8	0.73	0.67	1	0.58	0.67	0.73	0.66	0.38	0.02
7	0.62	0.6	0.63	0.61	0.46	0.58	1	0.57	0.51	0.57	0.42	-0.12
8	0.57	0.52	0.48	0.5	0.47	0.67	0.57	1	0.74	0.77	0.13	0.14
9	0.71	0.65	0.7	0.7	0.61	0.73	0.51	0.74	1	0.69	0.36	0.01
10	0.48	0.44	0.56	0.5	0.34	0.66	0.57	0.77	0.69	1	0.35	-0.02
11	0.39	0.4	0.55	0.45	0.31	0.38	0.42	0.13	0.36	0.35	1	-0.01
12	-0.11	-0.05	-0.15	-0.1	-0.13	0.02	-0.12	0.14	0.01	-0.02	-0.01	1
<p><i>Correlation between Variables Using Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient Matrix</i> Corr interpretation: .00 – .19 (very weak); .20 – .39 (weak); .40 – .59 (moderate); .60 – .79 (strong); .80 – 1.0 (very strong)</p>												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.50
2	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.76
3	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37
4	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56
5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.44
6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.88
7	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.46
8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.44	0.39
9	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.03	0.96
10	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.03	0.88
11	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.44	0.03	0.03		0.97
12	0.50	0.76	0.37	0.56	0.44	0.88	0.46	0.39	0.96	0.88	0.97	
<p><i>Rank Correlation p-values Matrix</i> Significant codes: Signif. codes: '****' 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 'ns' 1</p>												

In terms of significant association between the OCFUKs and RUK in Table 4.8, it shows moderate and weak correlation except for the leadership factor similar to the results on the correlation matrix. Individually, the median scores in Table 4.5 tells that the respondents agree on settling and working in the RDO in the UK long-term while agreeing also on all the OCFUKs which is quite similar to the response of the Filipino engineers with the individual OCFUKs except leadership factor in Table 4.8. Since the median scores for OCFUKs and RUK in Table 4.5 all agree, the weak, moderate, and no significance in Table 4.8 can have different results once the sample population is

made larger. The strategies formulated in the recommendation section were based on these significant factors *Autonomy and Freedom, Conflict, Communication, and Encouragement* with the latter two as priority since it has more statistical significance in this study.

Table 4.8

Relationship of OCFs and Retention in the RDO

	Organizational Climate Factor	Category	Kendall's Tau Coefficient	p-value	Association
OCFUK vs RUK	1 Autonomy and Freedom	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.34	0.0139	Significantly + weak
	2 Conflict	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.35	0.0105	Significantly + weak
	3 Communication	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.49	0.0004	Significantly + moderate
	4 Encouragement	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.41	0.0028	Significantly + moderate
	5 Leadership	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.27	0.0505	Insignificant
OCFPH vs RPH	6 Creative and Innovative Environment	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.02	0.8688	Insignificant
	7 Challenging Tasks	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	-0.10	0.4684	Insignificant
	8 Structure	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.12	0.4018	Insignificant
	9 Support	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	0.00	0.9779	Insignificant
	10 Identity	Scale 1 – 5, Ordinal	-0.02	0.8827	Insignificant
OCFUK vs OCFPH		Scale 1-5, Ordinal	-0.01	0.9672	Insignificant

Statistical tool used: Kendall's Tau Correlation Test; Statistical Software used: The R Software
*Significant codes: Signif. codes: '****' 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 'ns' 1*
Correlation interpretation: .00 – .19 (very weak); .20 – .39 (weak); .40 – .59 (moderate); .60 – .79 (strong); .80 – 1.0 (very strong)

On the other hand, in this study OCFPHs has no correlation and significant association with RPH. As seen in Table 4.5, RPH has a median score of two in which

respondents “disagree” to see themselves working back in a company in the Philippines in the future. Statistically comparing OCFUKs and OCFPHs, as seen in Table 4.8, without the consideration of retention demonstrates no statistical significance which means that the overall perception of the OCFs framed in the perspective of RDO in the UK was not correlated to the overall perception of the OCFs framed in the perspective of RDO in the Philippines. The OCFPHs might not also be relevant for the Filipino engineers in this study since their current perceptions depended on their current state being already in the UK.

One possible reason for no correlation and significant association on *Leadership* is the low rating of some respondents because the majority of them are in senior, managerial, and supervisory engineering position from their previous companies while the majority are still new to the current company which means they are expecting more from their current managers or supervisors. They are still in the training stage as new hires in the current company, and they are not given clear direction yet because their superiors expect them to be trained and orientated first. This can still be further investigated by increasing the coverage of the respondents which can be done in other studies and by reframing the question.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

This study has demonstrated that Filipino engineers' organizational climate factors in the RDO in the UK influence their retention in their current RDO in the UK which implies that the more they agree on the organizational climate factors in the RDO in the UK, the more they agree on working long-term and staying in the UK. In this case study, the organizational climate factors in their RDO in the Philippines do not have an influence on their retention in the RDO in the Philippines which implies that their agreement on their positive perception of the organizational climate factors in the RDO in the Philippines has nothing to do with their negative perception on seeing themselves working back in an RDO in the Philippines in the future. Nonetheless, the significant organizational climate factors that influence the retention of Filipino engineers in the RDO in the UK can be treated also as important factors that can be significant to Filipino engineers working in RDOs in the Philippines.

This study found that *Autonomy and Freedom, Conflict, Communication, and Encouragement* are indicative organizational climate factors in the RDO of Filipino engineers working in the UK. In the literature review, the leadership factor is the highest hit and most analyzed factor with a significant correlation to organizational outcomes. However, in this case study, the leadership factor is the one with no statistical significance among those five OCFUKs. Also, the perception of the Filipino engineers on the organizational climate factors in the Philippines did not show significance in this study. The Filipino engineers also agreed that they do not see themselves working back in an RDO in the Philippines in the future which is opposite to their agreement on settling and working in an RDO in the UK long-term. These

results might be different in other contexts and increasing the number of samples might reveal different statistical significance levels.

This study revealed that the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents are important attributes which define their unique characteristics as a group of migrant Filipino engineers employed in a *Semiconductor* R&D-based company in the UK. Their educational background and rich work experience are key requirements to their employment in their current RDO in the UK while their dependents, the easy migration regulation, and the remaining socio-demographic characteristics influence their migration decision. These organizational climate factors in their RDO in the UK supplemented by their socio-demographic characteristics influence their retention in the RDO in the UK.

Conclusion

This case study provided empirical results on the influence of organizational climate factors on the retention of Filipino engineers who are working in the RDO in the UK. Specifically, organizational climate factors such as *Autonomy and Freedom, Conflict, Communication, and Encouragement* positively influenced the retention in the RDO in the UK of Filipino engineers to work in an RDO in the UK long-term, while organizational climate factors in the RDO in the Philippines did not influence their retention to work back in an RDO in the Philippines in the future.

The study also provided the initial profiling of migrant Filipino engineers. The socio-demographic characteristics of the Filipino engineers that complement the organizational climate factors in the RDO. Filipino engineers are a unique breed of people with inherent characteristics such as being creative, innovative, educated, experienced, and highly skilled. These attributes together with the significant

organizational climate factors, being present at the right time, all contributed to the migration and emigration of Filipino engineers to the UK given the opportunity of UK RDOs to hire from outside their country and sponsor skilled worker visas.

This study showed that migration is a phenomenon that can entice highly skilled Filipino engineers employed in the Philippines to work for the RDO in the UK because of the latter's organizational climate factors that influence their migration decision. This implies that there is a need for R&D managers to formulate and implement strategies in the RDOs in the Philippines that will retain Filipino engineers.

Recommendations

Recommendations for R&D managers

A high-performing R&D organization is influenced by a desirable organizational climate where the creative workers are highly motivated displaying a favorable climate of *Autonomy and Freedom, Conflict, Communication, and Encouragement*. In order to achieve this desirable climate and to retain Filipino engineers, this study recommends the following strategies for R&D managers, based on the four OCFs with statistical significance and are indicative organizational factors of Filipino engineers:

- **Autonomy and Freedom**

It is an impetus for any RDO to provide its engineers with the climate for autonomy and freedom that will manifest their creativity. To achieve this, the R&D managers must empower their subordinates to become independent and confident contributors to decision-making. The R&D managers can allow their subordinates to attend project meetings, provide technical inputs and perform technical jobs with less supervision. Newly hired engineers need more supervision to do the actual work, but those experienced engineers already

have the expertise and skills, so they know much of what they are doing. They just need to be guided by R&D managers on administrative and managerial matters that are out of their technical scope.

- Conflict

Conflict is inevitable in organizations even in RDOs and thus there is a need for R&D managers to manage conflicts. There are many ways in order to prevent an organization from engendering excessive conflicts. Internal communication can be improved by having one-to-one meetings, team building, cross training, and gatherings like learning and conference sessions so that managers and employees within groups, as well as with coworkers from other teams or groups, could know each other well and build rapport. Induction for new employees is important because an engineer being introduced to workmates and their areas of work will not make them an outcast when working with other engineers. This will cut possible wrong perceptions and judgment as people are properly acquainted.

Having a climate where Filipino engineers can voice out technical and administrative concerns to their managers and freely give and take feedback to and from co-workmates in the RDO in the UK can help prevent team conflicts. With open communication within team and the organization, a positive nurturing culture of work-life balance and personal development can be achieved without roadblocks for instance. The Filipino engineers extremely preferred their working environment in the RDO in the UK because it is one without unnecessary conflicts in terms of its policies, bureaucracy and politics. This can be a good model for R&D managers and RDOs. The R&D managers must work

hand in hand with the top management to ensure policies related to politics, ethics, etc. are well in place.

- Communication

Regardless of the length of stay in the company, communication is always important. For new hires, the ability to surpass probationary period is the goal while for those already regular Filipino engineers, the goal is to thrive for at least five years until the application for British citizenship. In order to achieve these important milestones, the R&D managers shall be able to communicate properly to the Filipino engineers the goals needed to achieve regularization and career advancement stages. The R&D managers should consider internal communication as one of the important leadership skills in managing the engineers' objectives efficiently and effectively. They can employ regular one-to-one weekly meeting with newly hired Filipino engineers up until regularization while regular staff meetings with the whole team can be a good avenue for the managers to present key items for the team members to follow on their projects.

The team members can interact, flag for help and provide insights to the manager and other teammates. This is a healthy discussion not only between the manager and the team members but also a good exchange of ideas among the whole team. A weekly meeting, either at the start or end of the week, is good in briefing the important deliverables of the individual team members and the team. The proper documentation of the deliverables and projects saved in accessible and controlled locations can serve as offline communication between the manager and the subordinates. All these communication strategies can help the attainment of the goals of the Filipino engineers.

- Encouragement

According to the Filipino engineers themselves from the open-ended question, they can adapt and adjust in their current work experiences and situations in the RDO in the UK. Being able to adapt and adjust means that the Filipino engineers have experiences in various working scenarios and conditions. Part of the job role of the Filipino engineers is to solve problems in their designated areas. One reason why the Filipino engineers were hired in their current RDO in the UK is because of this, however; they are also new in the RDO, in its culture, and ways of working. The R&D managers, in most cases, are the ones who can provide extrinsic source of motivation from the outside to drive the intrinsic motivation of an individual engineer. The attainment of this will be made possible by having an encouraging manager and team. An encouraging R&D manager creates a supportive and motivating climate where the engineers can freely explore in trying to come up with creative ideas and solutions in the problems they face.

Encouragement can come from management support and can be more effective if R&D managers are collegial and team players with the engineering subordinates like when dealing with a certain problem where the R&D manager is both administratively and technically helpful. Engineers have highly technical skills gained from their education and rich job experience which the R&D managers also have. The R&D managers are more advanced in terms of knowledge and skills that is why they were promoted to managerial roles. The engineers are aware of when to consult the R&D manager while the R&D manager should also be able to know when to act and react with the engineers. The manager must always be ready to have an encouraging climate of

collegiality and professionalism that can foster creativity and ideas for both the manager and the engineer.

In summary, all these four organizational climate factors are important components of R&D management which are also associated with the important leadership and managerial concepts and tools needed in a productive and highly performing RDO. Autonomy and freedom are the most distinguishing feature of RDOs that produce output through the creative and innovative process while management of conflict, organizational communication, and encouragement are skills that have particular importance for R&D managers in managing RDOs.

Recommendations for future research

This study on organizational climate in the RDO and retention of Filipino engineers suggests future research that would add robustness to the design and generalization of results. Below are the methodological recommendations of this study:

- The organizational climate factors used in this study can be further tested to a larger population size of Filipino engineers in the UK or other countries which can employ random sampling and hypothesis testing of the relationship of organizational climate factors and retention of Filipino engineers. Other variables or organizational outcomes can also be tested in the hypothesis apart from retention such as job satisfaction and creative performance.
- Another area that can provide significant results on organizational climate and organizational outcomes of Filipino engineers is by comparison of different RDOs in the UK or different RDOs in different countries. This can be made possible by employing a cross-sectional study design in contrast with a case

study design wherein a number of Filipino engineers from different RDOs can be compared with each other. Having this larger coverage can also give opportunities for more comparison of the different subgroups of Filipino engineers such as managers, senior engineers, and junior engineers.

- This research has concepts which are not in the existing conceptual framework. These concepts are push and pull factors, and internal and external factors, which may also have a causal relationship with retention in the RDO of Filipino engineers or even with migration. These concepts can help construct a new conceptual framework from which a new research hypothesis could be derived and further tested by future researchers.
- This study used a quantitative approach, but it is evident from the answers of the respondents on the open-ended questions a potential for a qualitative component in this study which can relate the meanings from the interview or focus group discussion of the Filipino engineers to the quantitative results. Another study can also be pursued using a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches to generate a new theory and further test this new theory and hypothesis. In this case, the questionnaire and results of this current study can be used in a mixed methodological approach.

Migration is a wide and complex phenomenon and therefore a number of research and empirical studies are needed. Information and statistics on migrant Filipino engineers are significant for the Philippines while according to the DOST and other migration bodies, there is a lack of data on this area. Some of the recommendations for further study related to contents are:

- This study for researchers to further conduct research on this area that will include profiling of migrant engineers or other S&T personnel. The goal is to capture a wider array of data on engineers and other S&T personnel.
- This study used the OCFs in an engineering company and other researchers can test the OCFs in different fields of professions and context.
- This study encourages researchers to do policy research on migration of Filipino engineers as well as other science and technical workers. How can they be retained in the country is an important area of research to pursue because retention is one of the twelve key operational areas of NAST and DOST's thirty-year *Science, Technology, and Innovation Foresight*, entitled PAGTANAW 2050.

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Appendix A

Research Questionnaire

Part 1. Informed Consent Form

Anonymity and confidentiality of sensitive information will be preserved in the conduct of this research while the collection, storage and processing of the data using this form will align to the University of the Philippines Data Privacy notice which can be read from <https://www.upou.edu.ph/up-data-privacy-notice-for-students/>.

Your participation in this research is voluntary and you may refuse to stop participating at any time. To opt out in this survey, just stop answering and do not submit the *Google* form. For any query or clarification, the researcher of this study can be contacted via mstperez6@up.edu.ph while the program chair who endorsed the approved research proposal and questionnaire is Dr. Jaine Cadoc Reyes who can be contacted via jaine.reyes@upou.edu.ph / drdmprc@upou.edu.ph.

An automatic email response that will be sent to the respondent's email, after completion of the survey, will serve as a copy of this *Informed Consent Form*.

Please read each item carefully and tick the checkbox below if you agree to the following:

1. I have read the information above about this study.
2. I have received enough information about this study.
3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from this study at any time.
4. I agree to take part in the survey.

I agree with all the statements above. I want to participate in this study.

Part 2. Demographic and Background Information of the Respondent

Please provide the information being asked from the questions.

Name (Optional):	Age:
Sex at Birth: Male or Female	Civil Status: Single or Married
Do you have dependents? Yes or No	If yes to the previous question, how many dependents do you have? (Write N/A if not applicable)

Place of Birth (City and Province):	If you have dependent/s, do you live with your dependents in the UK? (Choose N/A if not applicable)
Where do you reside in the Philippines? (City, Province, and Region)	Where do you reside in the UK? (Postcode)
Undergraduate / Bachelor's Degree:	Master's Degree (Write N/A if not Applicable):
Institution (Undergraduate / Bachelor's):	Institution (Master's; Write N/A if not Applicable):
Year Graduated (Undergraduate / Bachelor's):	Year Graduated (Master's; Write N/A if not Applicable):
Doctorate Degree (Write N/A if not applicable):	Other Degree (Write N/A if not applicable):
Institution (Doctorate Degree; Write N/A if not applicable):	Institution (Other Degree; Write N/A if not applicable):
Year Graduated (Doctorate Degree; Write N/A if not applicable):	Year Graduated (Other Degree; Write N/A if not applicable):

Part 2. Demographic and Background Information of the Respondent (Continuation)

How long have you been working after graduation? (Including your work experience outside the UK; approximately in years)	How many organization/s have you worked with? (Including your current company in the UK)
Length of Stay in the UK (in months):	What is the name of your previous company?
What was your job title in your previous company?	What is your job title in your current company?
Is your current job role the same or related to your previous job role/s? (Yes or No)	Was your last job before your work in the UK, in the Philippines? (Yes or No)

Regardless of if you have dependents or none, do you financially support other individuals (e.g., parents, siblings, or others)? (Yes or No)	If your answer is no, please specify from which country was it? (Write N/A if not applicable.)
Do you still see yourself in the UK, five years from now? (Yes, No or Maybe)	A) How will you rate your working environment (transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate, and weather etc.) in the UK compared to the Philippines. (Range 1 to 5, Equally preferred to Extremely preferred)
How will you rate your company benefits and salary in the UK compared to your benefits and salary from your previous company? (Range 1 to 5, Equally preferred to Extremely preferred)	B) How will you rate your working environment (in terms of corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems) in the UK compared to the Philippines? (Range 1 to 5, Equally preferred to Extremely preferred)
How will you rate the reward and recognition scheme for your current company in the UK compared to your previous company? (Range 1 to 5, Equally preferred to Extremely preferred)	Do you think UK has easy migration regulations for Filipino skilled workers? (Yes or No)
Do you have relatives in the UK prior to your relocation? (Yes or No)	

Part 3. Please select from the five responses your level of agreement on the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
(1) I know my job role well and I also have freedom to contribute, decide and take part to					

projects in my current company.					
(2) We were encouraged to solve problems and issues creatively in my previous company.					
(3) I can easily voice out my concerns and give feedback to my supervisors or managers and co-workmates in my current company in the UK					
(4) My projects and tasks in my previous company are quite challenging.					
(5) I can easily relay information to my team and get responses from my supervisors and managers in my current company.					
(6) I can easily get approval for the resources that I need for my work in my previous company.					
(7) My supervisor in my current company encourages me to solve problems on my own but is willing to support once I ask for help.					

(8) I always get the support that I need from my supervisor and teammates whenever I need help from my previous company.					
(9) My manager in my current company in the UK gives me a sense of direction for my performance goals.					
(10) My manager from my previous company has a good training development plan and career growth for me.					

Part 4. Please select three (3) items below which are the most relatable to you.

	I know my job role well and I also have freedom to contribute, decide and take part to projects in my current company.
	We were encouraged to solve problems and issues creatively in my previous company.
	I can easily voice out my concerns and give feedback to my supervisors or managers and co-workmates in my current company in the UK
	My projects and tasks in my previous company are quite challenging.
	I can easily relay information to my team and get responses from my supervisors and managers in my current company.
	I can easily get approval for the resources that I need for my work in my previous company.
	My supervisor in my current company encourages me to solve problems on my own but is willing to support once I ask for help.
	I always get the support that I need from my supervisor and teammates whenever I need help from my previous company.

	My manager in my current company in the UK gives me a sense of direction for my performance goals.
	My manager from my previous company has a good training development plan and career growth for me.
	I have another reason/s not mentioned above.
If you answered you have other reasons/s, please specify. (Write N/A if not applicable.)	

Part 5. Please select from the five responses your level of agreement on the statement below.

I see myself settling in the U.K. and working in a company here (long-term) whilst becoming a British resident or citizen.	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I see myself working back in a company in the Philippines in the future.	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
What do you think could have changed your decision in applying, migrating, and working to a company in the UK so that you could have just stayed in your previous work?					
Do you have any other thing/s to say regarding Filipino engineers working in the UK?					

Google form link: <https://forms.gle/ADBdNVXYrjbWxWCT9> // End of Survey

Appendix B

Tables from the Review of Related Literature

Table 1

KEYS Assessment of the Climate for Creativity by Amabile (1997)

Scale Name	Number of Items	Description	Sample Item
Organizational encouragement	15	An organizational culture that encourages creativity through the fair, constructive judgment of ideas, reward and recognition for creative work, mechanisms for developing new ideas, an active flow of ideas, and a shared vision of what the organization is trying to do.	People are encouraged to solve problems creatively in this organization
Supervisory encouragement	11	A supervisor who serves as a good work model, sets goals appropriately, supports the work group, values individual contributions, and shows confidence in the work group.	My supervisor serves as a good work model
Work group supports	8	A diversely skilled work group in which people communicate well, are open to new ideas, constructively challenge each other's work, trust, and help each other, and feel committed to the work they are doing.	There is free and open communication within my work group.
Sufficient resources	6	Access to appropriate resources, including funds, materials, facilities, and information.	Generally, I can get the resources I need for my work.
Challenging Work	5	A sense of having to work hard on challenging tasks and important projects.	I feel challenged by the work I am currently doing.
Freedom	4	Freedom in deciding what work to do or how to do it; a sense of control over one's work.	I have the freedom to decide how I am going to carry out my projects.
Organizational impediments	12	An organizational culture that impedes creativity through internal political problems, harsh criticism of new ideas, destructive internal competition, an avoidance of risk, and an overemphasis on the status quo.	There are many political problems in this organization
Workload pressure	5	Extreme time pressures, unrealistic expectations for productivity, and distractions from creative work.	I have too much work to do in too little time.

Appendix B

Table 2

Organizational Climate Questionnaire by Litwin and Stringer's (1968)

Item	Variable	Description
1	Structure	The feeling that employees have about the constraints in the group, such as how many rules, regulations, and procedures there are; is there an emphasis on 'red tape' and going through channels, or is there a loose and informal atmosphere?
2	Responsibility	The feeling of being your own supervisor; not having to double check all your decisions; when you have a job to do, knowing that it is your job.
3	Reward	The feeling of being rewarded for a job well done; emphasizing positive rewards rather than punishments; the perceived fairness of the pay and promotion policies.
4	Risk	The sense of riskiness and challenge in the job and in the organization; is there an emphasis on taking calculated risks, or is playing it safe the best way to operate?
5	Warmth	The feeling of general good fellowship that prevails in the work group atmosphere; the emphasis on being well-liked; the prevalence of friendly and informal social groups.
6	Support	The perceived helpfulness of the managers and other employees in the group; emphasis on mutual support from above and below.
7	Standards	The perceived importance of implicit and explicit goals and performance standards; the emphasis on doing a good job; the challenge represented in personal and group goals.
8	Conflict	The feeling that managers and other workers want to hear different opinions; the emphasis placed on getting problems out in the open, rather than smoothing them over or ignoring them.
9	Identity	The feeling that you belong to a company, and you are a valuable member of a working team; the importance placed on this kind of spirit.

Appendix C

Tables Used in the Results and Discussion

Table 1

Socio-demographic Characteristics and RUK

Independent Variables	median	p-values	Significant difference
Age			
25-34 yrs. old (n=18)	4.0	0.2037	No
35-44 yrs. old (n=19)	4.0		
45 and above (n=2)	3.0		
Sex at Birth	4.0		
Male (n=22), Female (n=17)	4.0	0.7895	No
Marital Status	4.0		
Single (n=16), Married (n=23)	4.0	0.7994	No
Number of Dependents			
0 (n=15)	4.0	0.4321	No
1 (n=6)	3.5		
2 (n=10)	4.0		
3 (n=7)	4.0		
4 (n=1)	3.0		
Level of Education			
Bachelor (n=34)	4.0	0.5694	No
Master's (n=4)	3.5		
PhD (n=1)	1.0		
Length of Work Experience (years)			
1-10 (n=13)	3.0	0.2107	No
11-20 (n=23)	4.0		
21-30 (n=3)	4.0		
Length of Stay in the UK			
1-10 (n=26)	4.0	0.2265	No
11-20 (n=6)	3.5		
21-30 (n=4)	4.0		
31 and above (n=3)	5.0		
Aligned Job Role from Previous Work	4.0		
No (n=9), Yes (n=30)	4.0	0.1609	No
Number of Organizations Worked with			
2 (n=14)	4.0	0.7067	No
3 (n=8)	5.0		

4 (n=7)	4.0		
5 (n=9)	4.0		
6 (n=1)	5.0		
Support to Family in the Philippines	4.0		
No (n=10), Yes (n=29)	4.0	0.2592	No
Having Relatives in the UK	4.0	0.9731	
No (n=29), Yes (n=10)	4.0		No
Decision to Stay in the UK Five Years from Now	1.0		
No (n=1)	4.0	0.8066	No
Yes (n=29)	4.0		
Maybe (n=9)			
Rating on working environment (transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate, and weather etc.)	4.0		
3 (n=7)	4.0	0.7771	No
4 (n=18)			
5 (n=14)			
Rating on working environment (in terms of corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems)	4.0		
3 (n=7)	4.0	0.1558	No
4 (n=13)			
5 (n=19)			
Rating on company benefits and salary.			
2 (n=2)	2.0		
3 (n=12)	4.0	0.05764	No
4 (n=17)	4.0		
5 (n=8)	4.0		
Rating on company rewards and compensation	4.0		
1 (n=3)	5.0	0.4133	No
2 (n=1)	4.0		
3 (n=18)	4.0		
4 (n=12)	4.0		
5 (n=5)			
Migration Regulation	4.0		
No (n=5), Yes (n=34)	4.0	0.6345	No

Appendix C

Table 2

Socio-demographic Characteristics and RPH

Independent Variables	median	p-values	Significant difference
Age			
25-34 yrs. old (n=18)	2.5	0.7743	No
35-44 yrs. old (n=19)	2.0		
45 and above (n=2)	2.0		
Sex at Birth	2.0		
Male (n=22), Female (n=17)	3.0	0.2173	No
Marital Status	2.5		
Single (n=16), Married (n=23)	2.0	0.9633	No
Number of Dependents			
0 (n=15)	3.0	0.7960	No
1 (n=6)	2.5		
2 (n=10)	2.5		
3 (n=7)	2.0		
4 (n=1)	2.0		
Level of Education			
Bachelor (n=34)	3.0	0.0059**	No after Pairwise Comparisons
Master's (n=4)	1.0		
PhD (n=1)	1.0		
Length of Work Experience (years)			
1-10 (n=13)	3.0	0.8354	No
11-20 (n=23)	2.0		
21-30 (n=3)	2.0		
Length of Stay in the UK	3.0		
1-10 (n=26)	2.0	0.1560	No
11-20 (n=6)	2.5		
21-30 (n=4)	2.0		
31 and above (n=3)			
Aligned Job Role from Previous Work	2.0		
No (n=9), Yes (n=30)	2.5	0.7470	No
Number of Organizations Worked with			
2 (n=14)	2.5	0.5622	No
3 (n=8)	2.5		
4 (n=7)	2.0		
5 (n=9)	3.0		

6 (n=1)	2.0		
Support to Family in the Philippines No (n=10), Yes (n=29)	2.0 3.0	0.500	No
Having Relatives in the UK No (n=29), Yes (n=10)	2.0 2.5	1.000	No
Decision to Stay in the UK Five Years from Now No (n=1) Yes (n=29) Maybe (n=9)	2.0 3.0 1.0	0.0062**	No after Pairwise Comparisons
Rating on working environment (transportation, surroundings, cities, infrastructure, climate, and weather etc.) 3 (n=7) 4 (n=18) 5 (n=14)	2.0 2.5 2.5	0.9756	No
Rating on working environment (in terms of corruption, laws, policies, red tape, bureaucracy, and political problems) 3 (n=7) 4 (n=13) 5 (n=19)	3.0 2.0 2.0	0.4734	No
Rating on company benefits and salary. 2 (n=2) 3 (n=12) 4 (n=17) 5 (n=8)	2.5 3.0 2.0 2.0	0.8063	No
Rating on company rewards and compensation 1 (n=3) 2 (n=1) 3 (n=18) 4 (n=12) 5 (n=5)	3.0 2.0 2.0 2.5 3.0	0.7758	No
Migration Regulation No (n=5), Yes (n=34)	2.0 3.0	0.1482	No

Appendix C

Table 3

Pair-wise Comparison of Demographics with Significant Difference

Variable: <i>Level of Education</i>			
	Bachelor's	Master's	PhD
Bachelor's	-	-	-
Master's	0.062 ns	-	-
PhD	0.236 ns	0.236 ns	-
Variable: <i>Decision to Stay in the UK Five Years from Now</i>			
	No	Yes	Maybe
No	-	-	-
Yes	0.40 ns	-	-
Maybe	0.41 ns	0.41 ns	

Statistical tool used: Pairwise Comparison Using Wilcoxon Test

*Significant codes: Signif. codes: '****' 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 'ns' 1*

Although there is significant difference using the Kruskal-Wallis Rank Sum Test for more than two independent groups in Appendix C Table 5, there are no significant p-values from the Pairwise Wilcoxon Test as seen on Appendix C Table 8. This is due to the small sample size. That is, for the variable *Level of Education* ($n_1 = 34, n_2 = 4, n_3 = 1$) and the variable *Five Years in the UK* ($n_1 = 1, n_2 = 29, n_3 = 9$). With a small sample size, the power to detect significant differences in individual comparisons may be limited, leading to non-significant results in the post-hoc tests. Also, *Five Years in the UK* is a variable that should not be correlated to RPH.

Appendix E

UK National Semiconductor Strategy Excerpt

In order to achieve the vision of securing the UK as a world leader in semiconductor technologies, one of the execution focuses on skills and talent which explicitly says for the UK ecosystem to attract the skilled talents. One of the solutions to the problem of demand for skills needed to sustain semiconductor R&D in the UK is to welcome international talent. The strategy has a great campaign to encourage highly skilled international talent to live and work in the UK on techno. The recruitment of RDOs from the UK is being supported by the UK government by employing visa schemes such as the High Potential Individual Visa, Scale-Up Visa, and Global Talent Visa.

Source:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1157753/national_semiconductor_strategy.pdf

Appendix F

PAGTANAW 2050 Excerpt

Figure 1

Overview of PAGTANAW 2050 where Retention Is a Key Operational Area

Source: <https://nast.dost.gov.ph/index.php/pagtanaw-2050>